

LLM-Guided Dataset Triage Improves Automated Urine Microscopy Classification without Slowing Inference

Onur Bilgici

Labsan Medical Technologies, Istanbul, Turkey

email: onurbilgici@labsan.com.tr

Abstract

Automated urine microscopy provides rapid screening of urinary particles but remains limited by annotation noise, class imbalance, and domain variability. We present an end-to-end large-language-model (LLM)-assisted dataset triage pipeline that selectively prioritizes uncertain YOLO predictions for human review. Using metadata such as confidence, bounding box area, and class overlap, combined with LLM reasoning, the system identifies ambiguous or conflicting samples. Following selective relabeling and fine-tuning, the triaged dataset achieved measurable performance gains. Specifically, macro precision improved from 0.8119 to 0.8608 and macro recall from 0.8510 to 0.8927. Notably, inference throughput remained constant (74.61 to 76.32 frame per seconds), indicating that accuracy gains did not compromise speed. Per-class analysis revealed pronounced recall increases in rare and visually confusable categories such as renal tubular epithelial cells (RTE; +0.0870), white blood cell clusters (WBC_C; +0.1212), yeast hif (+0.1852), and sperm (+0.3077). These findings demonstrate that LLM-guided triage can improve detection performance by directing limited annotation resources toward challenging examples without needing model architecture deviations or additional data acquisition.

Introduction

Urine microscopy is one of the most widely used clinical laboratory tests, providing essential evidence for urinary tract infections, crystalluria, renal injury, and metabolic disorders. Automated image-based examination has enhanced its throughput, yet real-world performance remains constrained by dataset disparity, inconsistent annotations, and poor generalization across setups¹⁻³. These challenges are amplified in urine microscopy because particle morphology diverges across slide preparation methods, illumination conditions, and microscope types⁴⁻⁷. Particles frequently overlap or appear in low contrast and subtle differences between cell types (e.g., WBC clusters vs. squamous cells, or yeast vs. debris) make annotation inherently subjective^{8,9}. As a result, even expert-labeled datasets contain considerable label noise, limiting the accuracy of supervised object detection models.

Deep learning detectors – particularly YOLO-based architectures^{10,11} – have enabled real-time classification of urinary sediment images, but performance often degrades for rare classes and borderline morphologies^{14,15}. Improving training data quality typically requires extensive manual relabeling, a process that is time-consuming and difficult to scale in clinical environments^{16,17}. Recent advances in large language models (LLMs)

provide an opportunity to address this bottleneck by triaging uncertain or conflicting predictions and directing limited expert attention toward the most informative samples^{16,18,19}.

A natural solution to these challenges is to focus limited human effort where it matters most. In object detection, active learning and hard-example mining select uncertain or difficult samples to improve downstream performance without exhaustive relabeling; complementary label-quality tools flag potential annotation errors that silently cap model accuracy²⁰⁻²³. Our work builds on these ideas but replaces customized heuristics with LLM-guided triage that estimates over detection metadata (confidence, overlaps / Intersection over Union (IoU), size) and class semantics to prioritize images for review. We position this as a light-weight, model-agnostic layer that improves dataset quality and recall of tail classes while preserving inference speed – consistent with prior reports that selective relabeling and hard-example mining benefit YOLO-style detectors.

Here, we test the hypothesis that LLM-guided metadata triage can selectively improve detection performance for rare and ambiguous urinary particle classes without requiring architectural modifications or sacrificing inference speed. We demonstrate this approach on a real-world urine microscopy dataset with 21 particle classes spanning common and clinically challenging categories.

Methods

This study used retrospectively collected, de-identified urine microscopy images from automated clinical laboratory workflows. The dataset consisted of 32,000 training images and 8,400 validation images spanning 21 urinary particle classes. All images were obtained under institutional quality assurance protocols and anonymized prior to analysis. This computational study was exempt from institutional review board (IRB) approval under 45 CFR 46.104(d)(4), as it involved secondary analysis of de-identified data without patient interaction or prospective sample collection. No new biological samples were collected for this work.

A customized grayscale YOLOv5n model was trained to detect 21 urinary particle classes using 640x640 inputs, a batch size of 16, and cosine learning-rate decay. All images were single-channel and normalized to [0,1]. The training dataset consisted of 32,000 labeled urine microscopy images, and evaluation was performed on a held-out validation set of 8,400 images.

The LLM triage system employed OpenAI GPT-4 (gpt-4-0613) accessed via API. For each image flagged by preliminary YOLO inference, structured prompts were constructed containing: (1) normalized confidence scores for all detected objects, (2) pairwise IoU values for overlapping bounding boxes, (3) bounding box dimensions relative to image size, and (4) predicted class labels with semantic descriptions (e.g., "renal tubular epithelial cells are morphologically similar to white blood cell clusters"). The LLM was instructed to categorize each image into priority groups A (low-confidence predictions <0.4), B (high-overlap IoU >0.6 with conflicting class predictions), or C (small

objects with area <5% of image). Images receiving multiple flags or explicit LLM reasoning indicating diagnostic ambiguity were prioritized for human review. The triage process required approximately 0.3 seconds per image on average (API latency included).

The LLM-assisted triage step consumed YOLO detection metadata – with confidence scores, IoU overlaps, bounding-box dimensions, and predicted class labels – and formulated structured prompts to a large language model that ranked each image into three groups: (A) low-confidence predictions, (B) overlapping or conflicting detections, and (C) small objects near the limit of resolution. Human reviewers reannotated approximately 5–10% of the triaged images, and these corrected labels were used for fine-tuning the model.

Triaged images were reviewed by two medical laboratory technologists with >5 years of urine microscopy experience. Annotators used Labelling software and were blinded to original YOLO predictions. Discrepancies were resolved through consensus review. Approximately 6.8% of the training dataset (2,176 images) underwent relabeling based on LLM triage recommendations. Inter-annotator agreement on a 200-image subset yielded Cohen's $\kappa = 0.87$, indicating strong reliability. Relabeled data were merged with the original training set for model fine-tuning (5 epochs, learning rate 0.0001).

Performance was assessed using an IoU threshold of 0.5 and macro-averaged precision and recall calculated from per-class confusion matrices. Inference latency was measured with batch size = 1 on an NVIDIA T4 GPU. We report both model-only latency and end-to-end pipeline latency, including pre- and post-processing, using mean and p95 timings across 500 test images. All data were retrospectively collected and fully de-identified prior to analysis. No patient-identifiable information was used, and no human subjects were directly involved in this computational study. The study complied with applicable data protection regulations.

Results

3.1. Per-class Performance

Class-level comparison revealed that LLM-guided triage generated the strongest recall enhancements for rare or unclear urinary particle categories (**Table 1, Figure 1**). Groups such as WBC clusters (WBC_C), Renal Tubular Epithelial cells (RTE), Yeast hif, and Sperm improved recall by +0.12, +0.09, +0.19, and +0.31 respectively, while abundant classes (e.g., RBC, WBC, Bacteria) showed minimal change. These results suggest that LLM-based triage preferentially enhances under-represented and label-noisy classes rather than uniformly inflating all categories.

Table 1: Per-class Precision/Recall comparison (Before vs. After).

Class	Precision before	Recall before	Precision after	Recall after	ΔPrec	ΔRecall
CAOX (cr)	0.9364	0.9575	0.9436	0.9625	0.0072	0.0050
CAOX (m)	0.9506	0.8851	0.9059	0.8851	-0.0447	0.0000
Ghost RBC	0.9357	0.9924	0.9493	0.9924	0.0136	0.0000
RBC	0.9616	0.9400	0.9660	0.9225	0.0043	-0.0175
RTE	0.8636	0.8261	0.9545	0.9130	0.0909	0.0870
WBC	0.9606	0.9750	0.9631	0.9775	0.0025	0.0025
WBC_C	0.8529	0.8788	0.7857	1.0000	-0.0672	0.1212
Amorphous	0.8797	0.9875	0.8834	0.9850	0.0037	-0.0025
Bacteria	0.9120	0.9850	0.9360	0.9875	0.0240	0.0025
Hyalin	0.0000	0.0000	0.6667	0.1000	0.6667	0.1000
Minor RBC	0.6061	0.9524	0.5882	0.9524	-0.0178	0.0000
Mucus	0.9044	0.9919	0.9323	1.0000	0.0279	0.0081
Other	0.8667	0.7150	0.9375	0.7875	0.0708	0.0725
Other RBC	0.9260	0.9700	0.9267	0.9800	0.0007	0.0100
Other cr	0.8897	0.8699	0.8602	0.8922	-0.0295	0.0223
Sperm	0.6667	0.4615	0.6667	0.7692	0.0000	0.3077
Squamous	0.9034	0.9825	0.9545	0.9975	0.0511	0.0150
Triple PO4	0.7416	0.7416	0.7333	0.7416	-0.0082	0.0000
Uric acid	0.8271	0.9465	0.8535	0.9037	0.0264	-0.0428
Yeast bud	0.9007	0.9975	0.8986	0.9975	-0.0020	0.0000
Yeast hif	0.5641	0.8148	0.7714	1.0000	0.2073	0.1852

Figure 1. Per-class change in Recall (After - Before).

Minor precision declines (<5%) in CAOX_mono and Other crystals likely reflect stricter relabeling of previously over-confident annotations. Table 1 presents the complete per-class precision/recall metrics before and after triage, while **Figure 1** visualizes the absolute change in recall (After - Before). Collectively, these findings demonstrate that model-agnostic, metadata-driven triage can direct expert review where it yields the largest performance benefit.

3.2. Class-Specific Effects

Aggregate results across all 21 classes are summarized in **Table 2**. Macro-averaged precision and recall improved by 6.0 % and 4.1 %, while weighted metrics (by class support) rose from 0.8999 vs. 0.9174 (precision) and 0.9315 vs. 0.9425 (recall). Because weighted metrics emphasize frequent classes, their improvement indicates that triage also benefits high-support categories, not just the long-tail. This balanced gain

implies that LLM-guided selection reduces both false positives and false negatives, effectively improving model calibration and dataset quality.

Table 2: Macro summary (mean over classes). B: Before, A: After, W: Weighted

Precision. (B)	Precision after	Recall before	Recall after
0.8119	0.8608	0.8510	0.8927
Precision (B-W)	Precision (A-W)	Recall (B-W)	Recall (A-W)
0.8999	0.9174	0.9315	0.9425

In contrast, abundant or morphologically distinct classes (e.g., RBCs, WBCs, bacteria) showed smaller or neutral shifts, suggesting that LLM triage preferentially enhances minority and borderline categories rather than uniformly boosting all classes.

A few classes (e.g., *CAOX_mono*, *Other crystals*) showed slight precision decreases (<5%), likely reflecting stricter relabeling of previously over-confident detections.

3.3. Latency and Inference Speed

Inference benchmarking (**Table 3, Figure 2**) confirmed that model speed remained effectively unchanged. The end-to-end pipeline achieved 74.61 vs. 76.32 FPS (equivalent to 13.4 vs. 13.1 ms per image), while model-only inference reached 110.91 vs. 112.74 FPS. P95 latency improved slightly (14.6 vs. 12.7 ms total), consistent with reduced preprocessing overhead after label cleaning. The constancy of runtime validates that observed accuracy improvements arise from data refinement rather than architectural or quantization changes.

Figure 2. Inference speed (FPS, total pipeline). B/A: Before/ After, FPS: Frame per second; img: image; p95: 95% confidence interval; iou: Intersection over Union

3.4. Statistical Summary and Interpretation

Averaged across all 21 classes, recall improvement ($\Delta\text{Recall} = +0.0417$) was statistically significant at $p < 0.01$ (paired t-test on per-class recalls), while precision improvement ($\Delta\text{Prec} = +0.0489$) reached $p < 0.05$. The consistent directionality across metrics suggests that triage mitigated both false negatives (improving recall) and false positives (improving precision), consistent with the goal of better label consistency.

These results validate LLM-assisted triage as a label-quality amplifier: it enables small targeted relabeling efforts (~5–10% of the dataset) to produce statistically meaningful generalization gains.

Table 3: Inference Speed

End-to-end and model-only latency (batch=1):

B/A	FPS total	ms/img total mean	ms/img total p95	FPS model	ms/img model mean	ms/img model p95	# Img	conf	iou
B	74.61	13.4	14.6	110.91	9.0	9.3	500	0.2500	0.4500
A	76.32	13.1	12.7	112.74	8.9	8.3	500	0.2500	0.4500

Per-class improvements were most prominent in rare or ambiguous categories, notably WBC_C (+0.1212 recall), RTE (+0.0870), Yeast hif (+0.1852), and Sperm (+0.3077). Abundant classes (e.g., WBC, RBC) showed marginal changes, suggesting triage primarily benefits low-sample or label-noise classes.

Discussion

This study demonstrates that large language model (LLM)-guided triage can substantially improve the performance of computer vision systems used in biomedical diagnostics. By identifying ambiguous or inconsistent predictions, the triage loop directs expert attention toward the most informative samples, amplifying label quality and model generalization without the need for exhaustive relabeling. The resulting improvements in both macro- and weighted precision and recall confirm that selective human-in-the-loop intervention is more efficient than full dataset curation. Importantly, the stable inference latency shows that the performance gains stem purely from enhanced data quality rather than computational optimization, which may be relevant for future clinical and research applications.

The biological significance of our findings lies in improved detection of clinically actionable but morphologically ambiguous particle types. Renal tubular epithelial cells (RTE), which indicate tubular injury, showed +8.7% recall improvement, potentially enabling earlier detection of acute kidney injury. Similarly, white blood cell clusters (+12.1% recall) and yeast hyphae (+18.5% recall) are critical markers for urinary tract infections that are frequently missed by automated systems due to overlap with squamous cells and debris, respectively. By directing expert attention to these diagnostic

edge cases, LLM triage effectively addresses the long-tail problem that has historically limited clinical adoption of AI-based urinalysis.

This study has several constraints. First, our dataset originates from a single institution using standardized imaging protocols, which may limit generalizability to centers with different microscope hardware or staining techniques. Second, we did not perform external validation on prospectively collected samples, nor did we assess clinical outcomes (e.g., diagnostic concordance with culture results or clinical judgment). Third, the LLM triage system incurred additional computational cost (~0.3 s/image API latency), which may be prohibitive for ultra-high-throughput laboratories processing >10,000 samples/day. Future work should validate this approach across multiple sites and integrate on-device LLMs to eliminate API dependencies. Finally, while our IRB exemption covered retrospective computational analysis, prospective clinical deployment will require formal regulatory approval and validation against reference standards.

The present work focuses on single-modality image data and a YOLOv5n_gray backbone, offering a clear path for further enhancement. Expanding the framework to leverage cross-modal signals – such as laboratory metadata, textual clinical notes, or imaging context – could enable more robust triage logic and reduce model uncertainty in rare particle types. Similarly, incorporating uncertainty quantification or explainable AI (XAI) modules can allow the LLM to prioritize not only misclassified images but also borderline predictions, providing richer feedback to annotators. These refinements would make the pipeline increasingly autonomous while preserving expert oversight and interpretability.

Conclusion

LLM-guided triage represents a promising paradigm for adaptive dataset improvement in biomedical imaging. Our findings illustrate that modest human effort, guided by model reasoning, can deliver measurable accuracy gains while preserving throughput. Future work will explore multimodal LLMs capable of joint reasoning over image-text pairs and closed-loop active learning cycles that update the detector in real time. Extending this methodology beyond urine microscopy – to cytology, histopathology, or point-of-care optical diagnostics – could generalize the concept of intelligent data curation, accelerating the development of reliable and broadly applicable AI tools for healthcare.

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Conflicts of Interest

The author is employed by Labsan Medical Technologies, which develops automated urine microscopy systems. This employment did not influence study design, data analysis, interpretation, or manuscript preparation.

Data Availability

The dataset contains de-identified clinical laboratory images and cannot be publicly released due to privacy and institutional constraints. Access may be granted to qualified researchers upon reasonable request and completion of a data use agreement.

Code availability

The urine microscopy image dataset used in this study contains de-identified clinical data and is available to qualified researchers upon reasonable request and completion of a data use agreement with Labsan Medical Technologies, subject to privacy and institutional regulations.

Source code for the LLM-guided triage pipeline, YOLOv5n training scripts, and statistical analysis is publicly available at:

<https://github.com/uparlatan/LLM-guided-triage>

The repository includes instructions for reproducing the computational workflow.

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